

INFLUENCE OF TEMPERATURE ON THE SLOW AND INDUCED OXIDATION OF GLUCOSE IN THE DARK.

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Aqueous solutions of glucose containing sodium hydrogen phosphate have been oxidised in the dark at temperatures 10°, 20°, 30°, 40° and 50° by passing a current of air and the temperature coefficient of this reaction for a 10° rise between 10° and 30° is approximately 2.5 and between 30° and 50° it is less than unity. When the same reaction is carried on in presence of ferrous hydroxide as inductor, the temperature coefficient between 10° and 30° is approximately 1.8 and between 30° and 50° it is less than unity. When cerous hydroxide is used as an inductor the velocity of the reaction is greatly increased but the temperature coefficient is almost unity between 10° and 50°.

The slow and induced oxidation of glucose and other carbohydrates and of other energy-rich materials has been studied in these laboratories by several workers and the conclusions arrived at have been made use of in explaining the mechanism of oxidation in the animal body, plants and in soil. So far the experiments were carried on either in the diffused light or in bright light. But as the reactions in the animal body take place in the dark and under different temperatures, the study of these induced and slow reactions *in vitro* under these conditions may throw light on metabolic processes. The following experiments have been undertaken.

The reaction bottles employed were coated outside with Black Japan enamel to cut off light, carefully cleaned and dried and were fitted with rubber corks having double bores. Chemically pure glucose solutions together with inductors were put in these bottles and a current of air, freed from carbon dioxide by passing through a 50% solution of sodium hydroxide and tested by passing through baryta solution, was aspirated through the mixture in the reaction bottles which were maintained at various constant temperatures in thermostats.

The inductors used were freshly precipitated ferrous and cerous hydroxides and 20 c.c. of *N/10*-sodium hydrogen phosphate solution were also added to the glucose solution in the reaction bottle. The experiments were carried out at 10°, 20°, 30°, 40° and 50°.

After passing the total amount of air, the hydroxides were coagulated and precipitated by the addition of potassium sulphate. The mixture was filtered after warming it a little and the amount of unoxidised glucose was estimated by means of a standard Fehling's solution. Total volume of solution was 200 c.c. and the total amount of glucose in each case was equivalent to 0.2398 g. of CuO per 10 c.c. of glucose solution.

TABLE I.

Temp.	CuO corresp. amount after oxidation without inductor (100 c.c. soln.)	% Oxidation of glucose without inductor.	CuO (100 c.c. solution) corresponding amount with 20 c.c. $\text{FeSO}_4 \equiv 0.5 \text{ g. Fe}_2\text{O}_3$.	% Oxidation of glucose in presence of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2$ as inductor.	CuO corresponding (100 c.c. soln) with 47.3 c.c. cerous chloride $\equiv 0.1 \text{ g. cerous hydroxide}$.	% Oxidation of glucose with cerous hydroxide as inductor.
10°	0.2352 g.	1.84	0.2324 g.	3.10	0.1567 g.	34.60
20°	0.2286	4.51	0.2261	5.60	0.1557	34.96
30°	0.2134	10.94	0.2158	9.95	0.1465	38.75
40°	0.2252	6.01	0.2242	6.26	0.1350	43.70
50°	0.2296	4.01	0.2270	5.10	0.1220	49.00

TABLE II.

Temp. range ratio of vel. coeff.	Temp. coeff. without inductor.	Temperature coefficient with inductor.	
		Ferrous hydroxide.	Cerous hydroxide.
K_{20}/K_{10}	2.45	1.8	1.01
K_{30}/K_{20}	2.42	1.77	1.11
K_{40}/K_{30}	Less than unity	Less than unity	1.12
K_{50}/K_{40}	"	"	1.11

It appears from Tables I and II that the velocity of the oxidation of glucose goes on increasing up to a certain optimum temperature, which, in the case of ferrous hydroxide or in its absence, lies between 30° and 40°. In the presence of cerous hydroxide as inductor, however, the velocity of oxidation goes on increasing continuously and the velocity is higher at 50° than at lower temperature. The anomalous behaviour of cerium is interesting. As the body reactions take place at an optimum temperature, the above observations on the oxidation of glucose without any inductor and in presence of inductors *in vitro* may be utilised in explaining the probable metabolism of glucose in the animal body.